

COMMUNICATION AND INNOVATION IN HEALTH AND LIFE SCIENCES

Portfolio

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Transdisciplinary research: buy or bye?

Homo sapiens has a curious mind, and its destiny may be to uncover the mysteries of life and the universe, as well as to design tools to improve the efficacy and efficiency of our daily tasks. In his book *Sapiens*, Yuval Harari claims that mankind achieved its dominant position on Earth by being able to cooperate in large groups. Indeed, we may visualize lonely thinkers and scientists like Albert Einstein and Louis Pasteur when we consider science, but remember that knowledge from the past paved the way for the current researchers and therefore, science has always been a group effort. Besides this, scientists commonly discuss their findings with colleagues and may work in couples (Marie and Pierre Curie, Watson and Crick) or in teams. Nowadays, experimental findings in the (bio)medical field are all group efforts, often based on a collaboration between research groups from different parts of the world. Traditionally, they discover 'something' and this 'something' is communicated with the audience and where applicable used by society. This type of research is still common practice, but some scientists advocate the approach of social constructivism. Here, the role of science is not only dedicated to explain the world (realism), or to serve man's needs (instrumentalism), but knowledge is developed together with society. Transdisciplinary research is the answer; should we trust it?

Transdisciplinary research could provide 'socially robust knowledge' in a world facing complex, unstructured problems like climate problems and global poverty. Since it is not solely based on hypothesis testing, but integrates the relevant, non-academic actors with their experience as knowledge (Regeer & Bunders, 2009, pp. 39), solutions can be created from mutual respect and validation. From here we may suppose there is a larger willingness of the actors involved to apply the co-created innovations. Transdisciplinary research has already proven to be useful in the development of medicine against Aids, tells Barbara Regeer, associate professor at the Athena Institute. In the 1980's, a group of HIV-positive patients initiated a fund for a particular research line with a different focus than the 'mainstream' studies, which eventually made a large contribution to an effective medicine. A second example indicates how helpful the direct dialogue between patient and scientist can be; the efforts of scientists on skin-renewal development did not align with the (immediate) needs of the victims of burning accidents, who were mostly bothered by continuous itching. Upon participation in a transdisciplinary process, their voice was taken serious and a cream was developed. Both cases show that scientific development can be improved by including the knowledge of lay people.

Transdisciplinary research seems to have firmly rooted in the field of sustainability. This might come as no surprise, since the goodwill of many different societal actors are needed to handle this complex problem. During one of the honours courses (Designing Innovation for Sustainability) I could personally experience such a research practice; we were stimulated to work in groups with students of various study directions and instead of trying to solve a problem as fast as possible, the emphasis was placed on the design process. The very first step was to generate knowledge by having interviews with the different stakeholders and actors. The design process was not linear, but rather iterative with intermittent feedback. Before any commitments to a definite product were made, many possible variations were explored which integrated the needs of different perspectives. It was a creative process, and the result was something we could not have foreseen at the start of the project.

Even though inclusion of stakeholders has proven to contribute to scientific and technical development, it may coincide with several downsides. As has been explained, with transdisciplinary research the experience of social actors is accepted as knowledge and likewise consulted, from

where a strategy for innovation is established together with the scientist. This could easily become a tedious project, especially when multiple actors are involved with opposing perspectives. Barbara acknowledges the political aspect, but states that politics are involved in any type of research. Thus, to engage in 'open politics' is better than behind closed doors. She also stresses that the aim should not be to 'just collaborate', but to first agree on the main goal and shape the collaboration from there. For a successful project, the team should involve the most relevant actors, and where possible those actors who are open for collaboration from the start. During another interview, transdisciplinary researcher Hilde Brouwers further describes the importance of the team and building a bond with the actors, so they will not feel imposed by the suggestions of the scientist. In her current project the actors often contact her to ask for feedback. This suggests there is mutual trust indeed, and a continuous dialogue shapes the strategy. Like Barbara, she underlines the need for an open team and careful selection of the actors, since they have to invest quite some time and effort in the process. The result may be a much higher efficacy of the innovations, and for her as a researcher the satisfaction of a true contribution to both the societal and the scientific world. In her opinion, scientists should not observe situations and then write an article about it, but to use existing literature to help determine the strategy and eventually describe and reflect on the outcome in an article that contributes to the scientific and social community. A lot of information is out there, but it is either not concrete enough, or it can be combined in more structural theories and functional models.

Interestingly, a new field of work for scientists could have emerged with the transdisciplinary approach. And here the societal impact you make is more important than the numbers of papers you write. Fundamental research will remain essential to discover things we do not even know exist and may prove their functionality, but for the most urgent problems in our world, the race for papers between scientists will not resolve anything. I think it is time for scientists and (governmental) organizations to embrace the transdisciplinary approach and to start solving climate change and poverty right now, together. Just like Yuval Harari knows we excel at.

References:

Harari, Y. N. (2018). *Sapiens: A Brief History of Humankind* (Reprint ed.). New York, USA: Harper Perennial.

Regeer, B. J., & Bunders, J. F. G. , VU University Amsterdam Athena Institute (2009, June). *Knowledge co-creation: Interaction between science and society*. Den Haag, Netherlands: RMNO.

Why and how to Rethink science communication

Founded in 2019 as a three-years project, Rethink is a European Union's funded research program to study current science communication (SC) trends and to propose a model for an improved interaction/dialogue between science and society. Seven countries cooperate by forming separate Rethinkerspaces, where academics and local partners (like science journalists, museums and teachers) participate to map the interfaces used for SC. They also examine the effects of different types of science reporting on the public's opinion (sensemaking) and design and follow workshops. The Rethinkerspaces actively share their newly built knowledge with each other and construct protocols for investigation. So, is this the much needed forum to synchronize science and public, and will they deliver a concrete plan in 2022?

Of course we cannot look into a crystal ball, but it seems there is indeed good motivation to pay more attention to effective execution of SC with the complex societal/ecological problems and the emergence of digitization in our world. In that regard, this international research group has many problems to tackle. The fact that ever more people can find, but also place scientific content on the Internet, makes this project one of almost undefinable dimensions. As Bubela et al., (2009) point out, a shift of traditional SC has occurred, with not only specialist journalists translating and relaying scientific discoveries to the public, but also other parties taking this role with a "new emphasis on conflict and dramatic claims about risks and ethics". This way, scientific reporting becomes more framed, which results in polarization of opinions and fragmentation of the audiences. By framing messages, complex issues are simplified "by lending greater weight to certain considerations and arguments over others" that suits the ideological/political aims of the messenger or syncs well with the recipient. You may imagine that 'trueness' easily starts to diverge when framing is involved and this can contribute to a mistrust in science. Virgil Rerimassie, co-researcher in the Dutch Rethinkerspace, emphasizes the need to pull people out of their fragmented group or 'electronic bubble' and unravel the mechanisms of how people make sense of information they retrieve. Especially on social media, people are bombarded with (opinionated) information by means of tweets, pictures or short video's. These 'micro-moments' are valuable to understand and perhaps to use for SC intentions. A good example of how micro-moments can quickly influence individuals' ideas and leads to distrust in science, is the current 5G conspiracy theory related to the outbreak of Covid-19. Through social media it virally spread over a large public and even resulted in actions of arson by individuals.

Rethink's strategy to move towards a more open, democratic knowledge system and to facilitate more fruitful discussions or interactions between science and publics, was explained by Virgil's colleague Tessa Roedema. This past year was spent on studying the motivation of science communicators and to reflect on their role within the field. To dive deeper in the topic of sensemaking, they are planning 30 interviews on the communication around the Covid-19 crisis in the Netherlands. The selection on whom to interview will be based on three frames and searching for candidates will occur via the researchers' own (social media) network. Each of the other six Rethinkerspaces will organize similar interviews. Once a year, the research participants from all countries come together and follow workshops to implement the newly built knowledge with each other, but also to extract more knowledge.

So, is this working? On the Rethink website a first report was published in January 2020 and contained detailed information of the different digital SC sources per participating country. The sources were neatly categorized, quantified and strict protocols for finding these sources were included. Though this part of the study shows a systematic approach, the sample sizes mentioned by

Tessa are far too low to make any retrieved information from the interviews useful for generalization to the population or certain groups within the population. Besides this, the Rethinkers recognize the problems involved by people residing in their 'electronic bubble', but are themselves culprit of selection-bias when they recruit interview-candidates within their own, social digital network. As a biomedical science student I feel they should try to quantify the results for sensemaking like the way they handled the online SC sources. For example, they could analyze the information from the interviews to generate questions for large-scale surveys. In addition, experiments could be designed to simultaneously unravel mechanisms behind sensemaking and quantify the effects. A beautiful example of such an experiment is published by Bolderdijk, Steg, Geller, Lehman, & Postmes (2012). This group studied whether an environmental campaign with a message framed in a monetary/economic context was more successful than packaged in a moral motive. After their (perhaps surprising) finding, the authors argue that ill constructed messages can do more harm than good...

I am concerned about the fact that their transdisciplinary participant groups only consists of the SC 'distributers', but do not include the recipients. The involvement of these actors seems especially crucial during the workshops. Lastly, the Rethinkers mostly focus on digital SC. It is definitely a large source of SC and the newest, so it offers most to discover. However, zoos were not mentioned in the lists of SC sources, whereas I think those attribute significantly.

To conclude this writing; although progress has been made with mapping the different digital interfaces used for SC, I highly doubt if the Rethink program will result in more than preliminary insights in the patterns and mechanisms behind sensemaking. To truly provide the EU with guidelines on how to reach and target specific populations, or how to make best use of social media platforms by science communicators, more psycho/sociological research and in-field experiments are required. Interviews will not suffice, or a wider strategy must be designed from there, and SC recipients should be integrated in the Rethinkerspaces. Still, I am convinced about the necessity of transdisciplinary research in SC. On Facebook and within certain WhatsApp groups I encounter many people who are worried about the installation of 5G in relation to the spread of Covid-19 or have other health concerns. Although I believe there is no need to be afraid our brains will be microwaved, I also understand how the abstractness of the electromagnetic spectrum and radiation can lead to confusion and fear. In addition, mistrust is fueled by the notion science is losing its independence, since research is funded by the industry in several occasions. Better communication beforehand is therefore much appreciated, and, even better, involvement from society. Perhaps this mobile network conspiracy theory could function as a great model for the Rethink platform to study the process of sensemaking.

References:

Bubela, T., Nisbet, M. C., Borchelt, R., Brunger, F., Critchley, C., Einsiedel, E., ... Caulfield, T. (2009). Science communication reconsidered. *Nature Biotechnology*, 27(6), 514–518. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nbt0609-514>

Bolderdijk, J. W., Steg, L., Geller, E. S., Lehman, P. K., & Postmes, T. (2012). Comparing the effectiveness of monetary versus moral motives in environmental campaigning. *Nature Climate Change*, 3(4), 413–416. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1767>

Reinvent the fundament: System Innovation

The progress in technological development has substantially raised our quality of life, but has also created new, complex societal problems. Climate change, global obesity occurrence and outbreaks of pandemics are a few of many examples. These issues deal with a large number of different stakeholders and factors, so changes on a single level will likely act as a 'band-aid' instead of bringing forth a true solution. For this, the entire system needs to shift and therefore all relevant actors should be willing to make the needed adjustments. Transdisciplinary research may be a powerful tool to re-design systems and their fundamentals, from where new progress can be build.

The academic field of study dealing with system innovations assesses persistent problems, which threaten the sustainability of systems. Such problems usually exist for decades at one point in time and novel practices that acknowledge these problems (niches) experience resistance against their solution (Grin et al., 2010). Let us start with an example: In the Western health care system, product and process innovations are continuously introduced, but they seem to be unable to solve the underlying mismatch of supply and demand. In contrary, product innovations may have amplified a basic conflict in health care provision between the technically possible and the financially affordable (Schuitmaker, T. J., 2013). Furthermore, doctors are trained in a system which determines what diagnoses and treatments are possible. However, this system disregards for a large part the epidemiological transition that has occurred after successful battling infectious diseases by the medical field. Nowadays, chronic and degenerative diseases mainly threaten the health of the population instead of contagious diseases (Mackenbach & Van der Maas, 2008). Therefore, care and relief of suffering have become more important than cure for many chronically ill people, resulting in a growing demand for doctors who (also) fulfill the role of a mentor (Schuitmaker, T. J., 2013). Still, current health care policies system work according to the treat-to-cure model instead of treat-with-care, and place less weight on (what role the doctor can play in) prevention of disease. In the Netherlands, frontrunners of system innovation in the medical field address these problems in the Bewustzijnsproject, where they provide 'toolboxes' for (young) doctors, nurses and other medical personnel. These toolboxes may contain set-ups for health care workers to investigate and reorganize (administrative) problems they encounter while performing their tasks, an app for doctors to optimize their diagnoses, or a 'manual' to open up the conversation about operational costs. The main purpose is to involve all actors of the medical field to integrate their knowledge from experience and reflect together on the feasibility of approaches and treatments in relation to costs, long-term (side) effects and desire of the patient.

Where the Bewustzijnsproject may cater to the need for better diagnoses and care of the chronically ill, a 5-years research project from the VU Athena Institute focuses on healthy nutrition as a preventative measure of disease. In a conversation, biomedical scientist Cédric Middel explains how the experience of supermarket managers forms an integral part of designing an intervention. This intervention aims to stimulate the consumer in buying more healthy produce by using nudging techniques. These marketing techniques are not completely new, so the store managers have gained knowledge from applying and experimenting with the strategies in the past. During Cédric's project this information from experience is combined with more in-depth psychological knowledge and this should hopefully result in higher sales figures of fruit and vegetables, as well as a measurable benefit in health amongst the sample group. The research group and the cooperating supermarket are

occupying a niche in a system where the industry and governmental funding target on selling cheap, unhealthy products. By starting at the level of the grocery store and consumer, the hope is to create a successful enough strategy, which will have its snowball effect towards the other supermarkets. This could gradually change the current landscape of consumer experience, focus of the industry and subsidies from the government. For such a regime change we need the frontrunners or 'early adopters', like this supermarket chain, to take the first risk.

Half a decade ago a few entrepreneurs took a risk and acted as frontrunners by selling produce in bulk with a 'tapping' system, so the costumers could directly fill jars they had brought along. The set-up was to change the 'plastic culture' which is deeply rooted in the customers' sense of convenience, the supermarket operation, the wrapping and logistic industry. Most of these shops have already disappeared, but a new initiative has emerged; the Pieter Pot business has learned from the experience of these little stores, tweaked their idea and now apply a strategy where the jars with content are distributed via a 'green' mail delivery system. Customers order online and can exchange their used jars for new ones via deposit regulation. Here obviously, all knowledge has been gained by former experience and the whole expedition is, in fact, an experiment. The integration of scientific knowledge could be a successful move in this case. Firstly, a shift in culture and consumer experience is needed to make it work in practice, so socio/psychological knowledge may provide functional tools. Furthermore, it would be helpful to have insight in the ecological benefit of this expenditure (involving logistics and cleaning procedure of the jars) over individual plastic wrappings. Technological knowledge could upgrade a fill/tap system, which would perhaps be usable in actual store locations. A successful project of circular agriculture in Gelderland, Veld en Beek, applies a similar jar-distribution system for their customers. Veld en Beek cooperates with the Wageningen University to reach high levels of sustainability. I suggest to combine the innovative efforts of both frontrunners to gain a larger impact on the system.

In conclusion; where complex issues within society exist, innovation needs to happen within many levels and amongst many stakeholders for a successful solution. Therefore, transdisciplinary research is a logical approach of such system innovation. The Bewustzijnproject and the Athena nutritional study both involve actors from the field to develop interventions or new strategies. Pieter Pot mostly relies on the experience of actors, but may be helped with additional academic input from environmental and technological studies. Veld en Beek is actually a great example of such a transdisciplinary project (where the experience of farmers is combined with scientific knowledge) and could serve as a competent business partner for Pieter Pot, so their efforts can work synergistically to make a necessary shift in the system of nutrition. Let's reinvent the fundament.

References

Grin, J., Rotmans, J. and Schot, J. (2010), Transitions to Sustainable Development: New Directions in the Study of Long Term Transformative Change, New York/Oxford: Routledge.

Schuitmaker, T. J. (2013). Persistent problems in the Dutch health care system: learning from novel practices for a transition in health care with the UPP framework.

Mackenbach, J.P. and Van der Maas, P.J. (2008), Volksgezondheid en gezondheidszorg (vierde, geheel herziene druk Edition), Maarsse: Elsevier Gezondheidszorg.

<https://www.bewustzijnsproject.nl/>

<https://www.pieter-pot.nl>

<https://www.veldenbeek.nl/>

A lab or society grown scientist?

When Roger A. Pielke Jr. launched his book *The Honest Broker* in 2007 it caused quite a stir amongst scientists around the world. Here was a renowned man in the academic field, calling upon the societal responsibility of the individual researcher. With our current, complex societal problems (in large part caused by technological advancements) a 'hiding in the lab' attitude could no longer be justified. The work of every scientist carries a societal value, and should likewise be considered by the practitioner. In his writing, R. Pielke not only clarifies the various roles a scientist can play in the community, he also claims that science has become a tool for politics. To maintain the integrity of science, he urges the individual researcher to consciously choose one of the 'scientist' roles, which may include an active part in politics. As a future scientist myself, my attention is mainly drawn to environmental issues and animal welfare, and how I can contribute to the solution of these persistent problems. In that regard, I would like to discuss the introduction of lab grown, cultured meat, how the various roles of scientists would look like in this particular case, and to make a decision on what role would suit me best.

R. Pielke describes the Pure Scientist as someone who will share all the fundamental information in the process of decision making. Thus, during consultation by a member of the governmental advice committee for funding of lab grown meat, this scientist will deliver the annual numbers of methane and carbon dioxide emission by agriculture, the water utilization per kilogram of produced meat, and the total hectares of land dedicated to farming. He or she will also share the nutritional value of animal protein and fat, the average amount of meat consumption per citizen, and the types of (processed) meat which are associated with enhanced risk of atherosclerosis and cardiovascular diseases. The advice board will need to gather information per scientific expert to eventually extract the benefits and disadvantages over farmed meat versus cultured meat. They may give some considerations more weight, but it is still up to the political machine to decide over the funding. Along the route there are many moments where alternative interpretation of the data is possible, or a set of data may be completely missing. By keeping the academic field at this much 'neutral' distance, data can quickly deform to 'fit' the interest of a political group.

The Science Arbiter will not pull open the box of indefinite information, but provides the answers to framed questions. In this situation, the committee member might approach the scientists with questions like: "What is the current state of biotechnology and tissue engineering regarding in vitro meat?" and "what is the cost-benefit picture?". Like with the former role, society asks and science delivers. The normative questions concerning the issue are dealt with by the policy makers, either before or after information from the academic field has been collected. In this example it seems the debates about moral values of animal welfare and the use of animal stem cells for human exploitation have already been settled, and the first step is made to practical implementation. R. Pielke stresses the point that, although as neutral as both roles may seem, they often include 'stealth issue advocacy', and the values of the individual scientists slip through, either by the existing paradigm, personal preference for study topic or by research funding which results in conflict of interest. The author of *The Honest Broker* thinks "there is little room for arbitrating science in the process of decision-making and even good faith efforts to provide such a perspective can easily turn into a political battleground where political debate is couched in the guise of a debate over science (and the expert may not even be aware of his/her arguing politics through science)". Sheila Jasanoff (1990, pp. 249) agrees and adds to this statement: "Although pleas for maintaining a strict separation between science and politics continue to run like a leitmotif through the policy literature, the artificiality of this position can no longer be doubted". In short, scientists should be aware of their

political relevance and rather openly be engaged in decision-making than follow the means of stealth advocacy.

The third role, the one of Issue Advocate, features the open politics. This scientist will answer normative questions and tries to convince the decision-maker. An important part of his/her task is to reduce the choice of the policy maker. If this particular scientist is a pro-environmentalist, he or she would most likely put weight to the argumentation of reduced energy expenditure, the cause of animal welfare, and the rise of antibiotics resistance by agriculture. The current high financial burden will probably be placed in a prospective of quickly declining costs, and consumer motivation and taste experience may slightly get exaggerated.

The last role described by Pielke, and the one he urges more scientists to take upon themselves, is the role of Honest Broker of Policy Alternatives. This scientist will explore the question with the decision makers, before even trying to solve the issue. Thus, this serves to expand the scope of choice, but also to define the problem definition. Here it becomes interesting, because by going back to the question itself, we may come to the conclusion that the growing demand for meat is not the real problem, but our attitude to meat consumption. How much meat do we need for a healthy and well balanced diet? How much are we willing to pay for good quality meat? How far do we regard meat consumption as a basic right, instead of a luxury? What are the plant-based alternatives? How much funding is involved in the meat industry and how has this affected our view or culture of meat consumption? Would lab produced meat serve as a competitive solution for worldwide famine, or will it merely induce higher obesity rates? Will this innovation increase the sense of mankind standing apart from other animal species, and even apart from nature itself? Is this not merely an act of reducing animals to objects, using only the parts we want for our convenience? Do we need more meat on the world, or do we need to reduce our intake of meat? Is it morally correct to use the DNA program of an animal to grow only part of this animal for our consumption?

In quest of a rigid solution for environmental problems and with the right moral incentives, cultured meat from stem cells sounds like the logical answer, but I feel we have overlooked a few important possible consequences of this technological application. Since I would have liked to be part of an initial debate whether such introduction of 'fake real meat' would be desirable (supporting the stakeholder model of science), but there has been no such debate as it seems generally embraced as the correct solution, I now feel I would want to take the role of Issue Advocate to plea the contrary. That being said, I probably end up somewhere in between the Honest Broker and the Issue Advocate, for I merely want to show the alternatives to lab grown meat and open up the scope in regard to possible consequences. In addition, I may need to confirm that growing these cells in vitro is nothing like growing full body parts of an animal, or is comparable to shaving wool of sheep to knit a pullover. What I certainly know is, whatever practice I choose in the biomedical science field, I will always do this in consideration of my moral beliefs. If my work turns out to have a direct implication for the society, Issue Advocate is calling my name: I am grown in society and not grown in the lab.

References:

- Pielke, R. A., Jr. (2007). *The Honest Broker*. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
- Sheila Jasanoff. (1990). *The Fifth Branch*. Harvard, U.S.A.: Harvard University Press